

SR2609 Cruise Report

RV Sally Ride
May 22 – June 3, 2026

Recovery of the Aleutian Islands Internal Wave Resolving Array

Part of the National Ocean Partnership Program (NOPP) Global Internal Wave (NGIW) Study

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1. Cruise Overview

As part of the National Ocean Partnership Program (NOPP) Global Internal Wave (GIW) study (Buijsman et al., 2026), cruise SR2609 aboard *RV Sally Ride* served as the recovery cruise for an **Internal Wave Resolving (IWR) Array** located in the North Pacific Ocean south of the Aleutian Islands. The IWR Array is funded by the US Office of Naval Research (ONR) through an award titled “*A Distributed Network of Internal Wave Resolving Moored Arrays for Assessing Tide-Resolving Model Fields and Improving Forecasts in the Coastal Ocean,*” led by Scripps Institution of Oceanography (SIO) with subawards to Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI) and NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL). The PIs are Amy Waterhouse, Andrew Lucas, and Uwe Send (SIO); Magdalena Andres and J. Thomas Farrar (WHOI); and Jinbo Wang (formerly from JPL, now at Texas A&M). The IWR Array was deployed in a tidal beam that propagates southward from the Aleutian Islands.

The IWR Array (Figure 1) was deployed in July 2025 on AT50-39 (Andres et al., 2025) and collected measurements for about 10 months, with a subset of the data sent to shore in near-real time and available through the links at this site:

https://mooring.ucsd.edu/nopp2/nopp2_01/

The IWR Array combines instrumentation and technology from the Send Lab and Multiscale Ocean Dynamics (MOD) Group at SIO and the Current- and Pressure-sensor equipped Inverted Echo Sounder (CPIES) Lab at WHOI. This is the second deployment of an IWR Array; the first was deployed and recovered west of California (Buijsman et al., 2026) and overlapped with the Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) calibration/validation efforts (Wang et al., 2025).

Figure 1. Aleutians IWR Array with CPIES A1-A9 (A6 was not deployed) and a full depth hybrid mooring (CM).

SR2609 was also intended to serve as the recovery cruise for the **Longline Array** (Figure 2), another component of the observational portion of the GIW study, deployed across the continental slope south of the Aleutian Islands in a potential source region of an M2 tidal ray. The 10 km line comprises seahorse tilt current meters (TCMs) spaced every 500 m along the ground line with a

600 m vertical mooring at one end consisting of 15 thermistor and 10 TCMs. TCMs measure horizontal velocity and temperature. The Longline Array is funded by ONR through an award to Joe Kuehl at the University of Delaware working with Vitalii Sheremet, titled “*Aleutian Island Long-line.*” Unfortunately, due to ~3 weather days, there was not time to recover the Longline and a nearby CPIESs. This gear will have to be recovered **before September 4, 2027 1200 UTC**, which is when CPIES **A10** (comprising IES SN 448 and current meter SN 113) will auto-release from the bottom.

Figure 2. Longline Array (blue diamonds) and A10 (red dot) northwest of the IWR Array. Yellow star is Dutch Harbor.

1.1 Data Access

- Underway shipboard data collected on SR2609 will be archived and published with a citable doi number through Rolling Deck to Repository (R2R; <https://www.rvdata.us/>). In the meantime, the data can be requested from M. Andres or accessed at this link: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1WrvQD01ZQzrtQDv114Gq-63trnCoVUgC?usp=sharing>
- The raw time series data from the mooring sensors and the CPIESs are archived in the Send Lab.
- Processed data and derived data sets will be made available by the project PIs as processing and analysis progress.

1.2 Science Party

Magdalena Andres	WHOI/PO	CPIES	Chief Sci.
Jessica Kozik	WHOI/PO	CPIES	
Madison Zerona	WHOI Guest Inv.	CPIES/CTD	
Spencer Kawamoto	SIO/MOD Group	Mooring	
Isabella Franco	SIO/MOD Group	Mooring	

Argen Smith	SIO/Grad Student	Mooring/CTD
Mars Rafto	SIO/Send Group	Mooring
Charles Lindsay	SIO/Send Group	Mooring/CTD
Yang Zhang	SIO/Send Group	CTD
Joseph Feser	U Delaware	Longline
Res. Tech	Drew Cole	
Res. Tech	Jack Greenberg	
Inst. Tech	Bowman Halstead	
Captain	Ian Lawrence	
Chief Mate	Sebastian Grant	
Chief Engr.	Matt Peer	

1.3 Cruise Dates

Port: Seward Marine Center (U. Alaska Fairbanks), Seward, Alaska
Mobilization: May 21, 2026
At sea: May 22 – June 3, 2026
Demobilization: June 4, 2026
Local/ship time: GMT + 8 hours
AKDT

2. Cruise Narrative

May 21, 2026, Thursday

The two containers (from MOD and WHOI/UDel) were transported by the *R/V Sally Ride* from San Francisco, CA to Seward, AK and stored ashore by an expeditor during the intervening science cruise. These were loaded back onto the ship on Thursday, May 21.

May 22, 2026, Friday – May 24, 2026, Sunday

The ship left Seward at 0800 local and transited west via a route north of Kodiak Island and inside of the Shumagin Islands. Because of two strong storms impacting our instrument locations (Figure 3), we headed towards the north side of Unalaska (Dutch Harbor) to sit out weather.

Figure 3. Windy.com showing conditions on Sunday May 24, 2026 and prediction at the center of the IWR Array with predicted waves there reaching 32 ft.

May 25, 2026, Monday

This was a weather day with the ship tucked north of Unalaska. We took the opportunity to do a CTD test cast to 500 m depth (CTD #1; SR2609_CTD01.hex) and triggered all the bottles to test for leaks. We collected water samples for salinity measurements on shore. Then we spent the day jogging east and west north of Unalaska.

May 26, 2026, Tuesday

We started heading west towards Samalga Pass at 0800 local. It was a rough ride. That evening as we approached the pass, we had to decide whether there was going to be time to recover the Longline and CPIES A10 before transiting south to the IWR Array. Since we already lost ~2 days to bad weather (slow transits and sitting in the lee) and bad weather was also predicted to slow the

eventual transit back to Seward, we decided to forego the Longline and CPIES. It was a rough night.

May 27, 2026, Wednesday

After passing through Samalga Pass, we started heading south to CPIES **A3 (SN 449; CM 263)** at the northern side of the IWR Array. We arrived at A3 at 1630 local. We sent the release command at 16:45 and the instrument surfaced ~200 m off the starboard bow and was on board by 18:03. The ship's radio direction finder (RDF) was able to hear this CPIES's radio beacon (along with all of the subsequent CPIES), but the bearing isn't correct (perhaps because the antenna isn't high enough). Even without a correct bearing, it was a very helpful confirmation of the CPIES's surfacing to have the radio beacon (especially in a few cases where we had trouble finding the CPIES visually). We used the ship's through hull transducer with the CPIES Lab's 8011M deckbox and the receive level set to ~7-9 (default is 4), depending on the station. In a few cases we also used the MOD Lab's 8011M deckbox and over-the-side transducer as backup and confirmation that the through hull transducer setup was working properly (it was).

After this, we transited to CPIES **A4 (SN 450; CM 258)**. This site happens to have a NOAA Tsunami Buoy nearby. We were on station by 1930 local. We sent the release command at 1937. At first the release pinging worked as expected (12 kHz, 4 sec rate) but about 7 minutes into the burn wire process the pinger stopped. We used the over the side transducer to verify that the problem was with the CPIES, not the ship's transducer. Nevertheless, the CPIES surface at the expected time (15-minute burn plus 54-minute rise through the water column) and we had the CPIES aboard by 2100. The strobe and radio beacon were working, but the CPIES still wasn't pinging when we had it on board. It did ping as expected (1 ping followed by 2 pings) when it was connected to Motocross to reset the release relay and check the time. We will have to troubleshoot back in the lab to see what happened.

Next we headed to **A5 (SN 451; CM 259)** and arrived on station about 2030 local. We sent the release command at 2037 and had the CPIES onboard by midnight.

May 28, 2026, Thursday

We had the next CPIES, **A7 (SN 454; CM 262)** released by 0236 and on board about 1.5 hours later. This recovery was the first one that was in the dark and the strobe was a useful recovery aid. By 0420 we started heading towards the central mooring to conduct a full-depth CTD cast near the mooring and CPIES A9.

CTD #2 (SR2609_02.hex) was a full water column CTD to 5285 m, without any sensors connected to the CTD. The cast was started around 0600 local and was complete by 0930 local. After this we prepared to recover the nearby **central mooring** with the release command sent around 1000. The mooring was recovered top first. Recovery went well, though there were some challenging wuzzles ([Figure 4](#)). The anchor release was on deck by 1500 local.

Figure 4. Recovery of the central full-depth hybrid mooring in the IWR Array.

We then repositioned the ship to recover CPIES A9 (SN 457; CM265). We sent the RELEASE command at 1547 local and had the CPIES on deck by 1712 local.

We then continued to CPIESs A8 (SN 456; CM 264). We were able to see the instrument sampling (with the TRAX program running on the Toughbook computer), both during the ship's approach to the site and while we were sitting on station. However, we were unable to release the instrument from the bottom. We initially used the ship's through hull transducer with the CPIES Lab's 8011M deckbox (which had worked well at all the previous sites). We tried different combinations of output level and receive level, but got no responses from the CPIES, neither for CLEAR nor RELEASE. We tried unplugging the deckbox from ship's power, made sure all the external 12 kHz noise (e.g. the ship's speed log, the multibeam) was turned off. We also tried several times with the ship as quiet as possible (e.g. with the bow thrusters off) and tried repositioning the ship. We also tried the MOD group's over the side transducer. We think it is likely that the problem is not with noise obscuring the commands sent by us to the CPIES, but rather that there is a problem in the CPIES's listening (drifting electronics that affect the internal filtering?). At any rate, we were unable to retrieve A8. The instrument is still sampling on site (a set of 16 12 kHz pings every 10 minutes). At deployment it was programmed to auto-release from the bottom on **September 5 2027 1200 UTC**.

We transited to CPIES A1 (SN 445; CM 254). As with several of the previous CPIES, since we were listening with the ship's through hull transducer, we were able to see the instrument sampling (with TRAX run on the Toughbook) on our approach to the site. We sent a CLEAR command during the approach and the CPIES responded with the expected 2-ping reply. While still underway we then sent the RELEASE command and the CPIES recognized the command and started the burn wire process. The RELEASE command was sent at 2140 local and the CPIES was on deck by 2057 local.

May 29, 2026, Friday

We reached the final CPIES site, A2 (SN 453; CM 261) around 0019 local. We sent the RELEASE command at 1227. The other CPIES generally had come up off the starboard bow, however this one popped up off the starboard quarter, quite close to the ship. This recovery was in the dark, so the strobe was helpful since the ship's radio direction finder doesn't provide accurate bearing. The

CPIES was aboard by 0141 local. The current meter cable (rather the float recovery line) was grappled during this CPIES recovery, so we'll have to check the cable (and the port through the IES glass) for any damage when we are back in the lab.

We left the IWR Array site and started transiting towards Seward in anticipation of poor weather during the middle of the homebound transit (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Windy.com's Saturday, 5/30/2026 prediction for waves (left) and wind (right) expected on Monday 6/1/2026 during the transit back to Seward.

May 30, 2026, Saturday

Our planned transit happened to bring us very close to a wave glider from Mark Zumberge's lab, so we were able to accommodate their request for a wave glider rescue near 53° 09.0N 163° 51.0W. The instrument was aboard by 0730 local and secured on impromptu cushioning on our wire baskets in the hangar (Figure 6). We turned it off with a magnet on Sunday May 31, 2026 at 1006 local.

Figure 6. Wave glider rescue and storage in the hangar.

We continued on the transit until 0830 local when we stopped to conduct a calibration CTD (CTD#3; SR2609_CTD03.hex) to 3000 m depth with instrumentation from the mooring strapped to the rosette. The cast included soaking at depths for 10 minutes and included bottles samples for shoreside salinity measurements. During the cast we saw several whales. One of them was identified as PWF-NP_2869, a humpback whale that had migrated from Hawaii (Figure 7).

Figure 7. (Top) whale fluke used to ID PWF-NP_2869 (photo credit: M. Zerona). (Bottom) this individual has now been spotted 5 times. The most recent previous sighting was off Maui on Dec. 12, 2025. <https://happywhale.com/individual/50831;enc=668804> .

Cast#3 was finished by 1115 local and we continued along the transit. We stopped at 1215 local to conduct the next calibration CTD (CTD#4; SR2609_CTD04.hex) to 2000 m depth. This cast was complete by 1430 and we continued the transit for about one hour. The final calibration cast (CTD#5; SR2609_CTD05.hex) to 750 m depth was started around 1445 and completed by 1715 local.

May 31, 2026, Sunday

Transit; good weather. We turned off the wave glider (with a magnet) around 1000 local.

June 1, 2026, Monday

Transit and then tucked in north of Kodiak due to weather.

June 2, 2026, Tuesday

Transit.

June 3, 2026, Wednesday

Arrived Seward, AK at the University of Alaska Marine Center at 0900. We packed the gear into the SIO 20 ft. container and the UDel/WHOI 20 ft. container and loaded an East Coast winch onto *Ride*. The UDel/WHOI container included (1) spent mooring wire to be disposed of at WHOI and two lengths of mooring wire to be strength tested at WHOI and (2) a winch block to be transported back to the East Coast Winch Pool. The containers and winch will ride the vessel to Newport, OR, where they will be offloaded to trucks returning to SIO and WHOI. At present the ship is expected to arrive at 1400 on June 14, 2026 at OSU Marine Operations (2020 SE Marine Science Drive, Newport, OR 97365).

Post-cruise note: there seems to be a calibration error in the ship's scale.

- After the cruise, the SIO container was packed such that it would weigh approximately 19,000 lbs and this was deemed doable for the limits for both the *Ride*'s ship crane and for the OSU pier's forklift. Noah Howins (SIO) was on site in Newport, OR for the ship's arrival (June 14) and found out that the ship's crane was reading 22,700 lbs and so they had to scramble to get items out of the container until it read around 19,000 lbs and then they offloaded it. When the container arrived to SIO, the MOD group weighed it using the portable container scales (<https://www.bison-jacks.com/container-weighing/portable-container-scales/>) and showed that the container was far below the *Ride*'s crane measured value.
- There was already indication of a miscalibration on the outbound cruise (from San Francisco): the SIO groups had estimated 10,700 lbs for the SIO container and when Matt Durham confirmed receipt, he stated the weight at 12,300 lbs. Similarly, Sean Whelan from WHOI had said the container from WHOI was 7,200 lbs and Matt's receipt confirmation has it at 7,800 lbs.

3. References

Andres, M., M. Tominaga, S. Kelley, G. Packard, and M. Tivey, (2025). AT50-39 Cruise Report. Zenodo. [10.5281/zenodo.16273010](https://zenodo.org/record/16273010).

Buijsman, M., A. Waterhouse, et al., (2026). A Multi-Agency Experiment on Internal Wave Energy, Mixing, and Interactions and their Representation in Global Ocean Models and Operational Forecasts. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, doi:10.1175/BAMS-D-24-0174.1

Wang, J., A.J. Lucas, S. Stalin, M. Lankhorst, U. Send, O. Schofield, et al. (2025). SWOT mission validation of sea surface height measurements at sub-100 km scales. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 52, e2025GL114936. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2025GL114936>

4. Appendix

4.1 Deployment Information

Information about the instrument deployments from the AT50-39 cruise in July 2025 (Andres et al., 2025) is copied below in Table 1 and Table 2:

Table 1. CPIES Deployments

Actual CPIES Locations:															
Site ID	CPIES SN	Commands			CM SN	CPIES Deployment Location ¹					Depth (m) ²	Deployment		Autorelease Date	
		TIm/Xpnd/Bcn	Rel			lat	lon	lat	lon	Date		Time (UTC)			
A1	445	65/69/73	61		254	49.5002	-169.0843	49	30.014 N	169	5.058 W	5329	11-Jul-25	16:34:42	Sept. 1, 2027 12
A2	453	67/71/75	5		261	49.6908	-169.2061	49	41.448 N	169	12.367 W	5329	11-Jul-25	19:57:21	Sept. 4, 2027 12
A3	449	66/70/74	1		263	49.7696	-169.4988	49	46.177 N	169	29.926 W	5336	8-Jul-25	14:37:55	Sept. 9, 2027 12
A4	450	67/71/75	2		258	49.6898	-169.7920	49	41.390 N	169	47.520 W	5130	8-Jul-25	21:27:00	Sept. 8, 2027 12
A5	451	65/69/73	3		259	49.4967	-169.9089	49	29.801 N	169	54.531 W	5382	8-Jul-25	4:29:38	Sept. 3, 2027 12
A6	No CPIES Deployed at this site														
A7	454	65/69/73	6		262	49.2305	-169.4992	49	13.828 N	169	29.950 W	5279	9-Jul-25	15:18:00	Sept. 7, 2027 12
A8	456	67/71/75	8		264	49.3088	-169.2054	49	18.527 N	169	12.326 W	5381	9-Jul-25	22:46:00	Sept. 5, 2027 12
A9	457	65/69/73	9		265	49.4993	-169.5172	49	29.957 N	169	31.033 W	5380	11-Jul-25	0:29:15	Sept. 5, 2027 12
A10	448	65/69/73	0		113	51.9990	-170.9987	51	59.939 N	170	59.920 W	3707	14-Jul-25	5:08:51	Sept. 4, 2027 12

¹ Currents were relatively weak during deployment, so we are assuming the CPIESs did not drift substantially during descent

² Depth from ship's multibeam

Table 2. Central Mooring and Longline Array Deployments

Site ID	lat	lon	lat	lon	Depth (m) ²	Date	Time (UTC)
CM ¹	49.5000	-169.5000	49	30.000 N 169 30.000 W	5376	10-Jul-25	23:07:00
LL_north	52.2304	-171.3027	52	13.826 N 171 18.160 W	629	13-Jul-25	17:11:25
LL_south	52.1581	-171.2256	52	9.485 N 171 13.535 W	966	13-Jul-25	19:16:06

¹This is the estimated location on the bottom assuming a 700 m fall back. The anchor drop coordinates are: 49° 30.0031 N; 169° 30.6306 W

² Depth from ship's multibeam

4.2 Recovery Information

For each CPIES, we used Motocross to check the IES clock against UTC in time.gov:

Table 3. CPIES Clock Drifts

Site ID	CPIES SN	Deployment		Recovery		time.gov	IES time	IES Clock Drift (s) ¹	IES Clock Drift (min)
		Date	Time (UTC)	Date	Time (UTC)				
A1	445	11-Jul-25	16:34:42	29-May-26	5:40:00	7:14:45	7:13:08	-97	-1.62
A2	453	11-Jul-25	19:57:21	29-May-26	8:27:00	9:51:50	9:49:52	-58	-0.97
A3	449	8-Jul-25	14:37:55	28-May-26	0:45:00	2:45:15	2:44:10	-65	-1.08
A4	450	8-Jul-25	21:27:00	28-May-26	3:37:00	5:27:00	5:26:04	-56	-0.93
A5	451	8-Jul-25	4:29:38	28-May-26	6:37:00	8:25:30	8:24:47	-43	-0.72
A6	No CPIES Deployed at this site								
A7	454	9-Jul-25	15:18:00	28-May-26	10:36:00	12:28:45	12:27:08	-97	-1.62
A8	456	9-Jul-25	22:46:00	Unresponsive to ACS commands; autorelease Sept. 5, 2027 12 UTC					
A9	457	11-Jul-25	0:29:15	28-May-26	23:47:00	1:22:00	1:20:18	-102	-1.70
A10	448	14-Jul-25	5:08:51	Unable to visit site due to weather; autorelease Sept 4, 2027 12 UTC					

¹ negative means IES is late

Five CTD casts were conducted (Table 4), and bottles of seawater were collected at several depths to bring back to shore to measure salinity with a salinometer. The first, CTD#1, was a test cast. CTD#2 was a full depth CTD taken near A9 and the Central Mooring before they were recovered. CTD#3-5 were casts with instruments attached to the rosette as listed in Table 5.

Table 4. SR2609 CTD Cast Locations

	Date	Latitude	Longitude	Water Depth (m)	Cast Depth (m)	File name
CTD#1	2026-May 25	54° 04.63'N	166 ° 40.10'W	615	500	SR2609_CTD01.hex
CTD#2	2026-May-28	49° 29.77'N	169° 29.74'W	5301	5285	SR2609_CTD02.hex
CTD#3	2026-May-30	53° 15.68'N	163° 39.56'W	4248	3000	SR2609_CTD03.hex
CTD#4	2026-May-30	53° 21.63'N	163° 29.23'W	4180	1950	SR2609_CTD04.hex
CTD#5	2026-May-30	53° 26.69'N	163° 20.41'W	4255	700	SR2609_CTD05.hex

Table 5. Instrument Calibrations on SR2609 CTD Casts

	Instruments	Instrument Calibration Cast Sample Rate (s)	Depth Rating (m)	Stop Depths (m)	Operation		
Shallow cast-700m	SBE37 (2)	10	1000	Bottom	Fire Bottle & 10 Min Soak	SBE37 #24286	1000
700m MAX	RBR Concerto (1)	2	750	low-gradient zone near 500	10 Min Soak	SBE37 #24285	1000
	RBR SoloT (19)	2	1700	low-gradient zone near 300	10 Min Soak		
	RBR Duet (4)	2	1700	low-gradient zone near 100	10 Min Soak		
				8	Fire Bottle & 10 Min Soak		
Midwater cast-1950m	SBE37 (1)	10	2000	Bottom	Fire Bottle & 10 Min Soak	SBE37 #24271	2000
1950m MAX	SBE37 (2)	10	3500	1700	10 Min Soak	SBE37 #24274	3500
				1300	Fire Bottle & 10 Min Soak	SBE37 #6363	3500
				low-gradient zone near 500	10 Min Soak		
				8	Fire Bottle & 10 Min Soak		
Deep Cast-Full Depth	SBE37 (3)	10	7000	Bottom (near 3000)	Fire Bottle & 10 Min Soak	SBE37 #6355	7000
7000m MAX	RBR SoloT Ti (24)	2	10,000	2100	Fire Bottle & 10 Min Soak	SBE37 #24275	7000
				1200	Fire Bottle & 10 Min Soak	SBE37 #24276	7000
				800	Fire Bottle		
				100	Fire Bottle		
				8	Fire Bottle & 10 Min Soak		
All other casts	n/a		n/a	~3 per cast, distributed in depth range 1000 - 5500 m	Fire Bottle & 5 sec soak		

4.3 Mooring Diagram with Recovery Notes

Photos documenting the recovery of mooring sensors were collected by Y. Zhang and C. Lindsay are available here: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1_NOwp_B9X9o-2dPccx8BT04e_mV4VxOj?usp=drive_link.

NOPP2-1 Deployed			
Hybrid Mooring (Profiler + Fixed-Depth) with 2 49-Inch Spheres and NOPP Instruments, Deployed			
By: C. Ewert		REV: M	
Source: 28-Apr-2026 11:10:41, ...NOPP\NOPP2-1\NOPP2_1_deployed\nopp2_1_deployed.cfg			
Author: 28-Apr-2026 11:10:48, cewert@(PCWIN64)			
depth (incl. stretch)	component description	S/N	Distance from Upper / Lower rope end

!!! Check ALL shackles for cotter pins !!!

July-7-2025 May-20-2026

out of water
UTC time

depth (incl. stretch)	component description	S/N	Distance from Upper / Lower rope end	in/out of water comment
597 m	Cable Float CF-12		197.0 3.0	positive wire in reverse catenary
602 m	49" Float (Rated 1500 m) Apollo X7 #1373		AS 21 3/4" AS 21 1/2" EM Swivel 31 PL 21 5/8"	2.2m (7.3') bypass Custom shackle 14mm 316SS in 1/2 AS Custom shackle 14mm 316SS in 1/2 AS
606 m	ADCP Instr., T-RDI 75 kHz #24912 ID 03		AS 21 1/2" AS 21 1/2"	17:49
607 m	ADCP Instr., T-RDI 75 kHz #13481 ID 04		6.5m (21.3')	19:33
606 m	Temp. Instr. RBR Solo-T #238062		1.0	17:49
607 m	CTD Inst., w/ pres(rated 1000 m) SBE37-IM MC #24285 ID 85		1149.0 2.0 1148.0	17:49 } 19:47
615 m	Temp. Instr. RBR Solo-T #238063		10.0 1140.0	17:54 } 19:53
625 m	Temp. Instr. RBR Solo-T #238064		20.0 1130.0	17:55 } 19:54
640 m	Temp. Instr. RBR Solo-T #238065		35.0 * 1135	17:57 } 19:55
650 m	Temp. Instr. RBR Solo-T #238066		45.0 1105.0	17:58 } 19:57
660 m	Temp. Instr. RBR Solo-T #238067		55.0 1095.0	17:59 } 19:58
675 m	Temp. Instr. RBR Solo-T #238068		70.0 1080.0	18:00 } 19:59
685 m	Temp. Instr. RBR Solo-T #238069		80.0 1070.0	18:01 } 20:00
695 m	Temp. Instr. RBR Solo-T #238070		90.0 1060.0	18:01 } 20:00
710 m	Temp. Instr. RBR Solo-T #238071		105.0 1045.0	18:02 } 20:01
720 m	Temp. Instr. RBR Solo-T #238072		115.0 1035.0	18:03 } 20:02
730 m	Temp. Instr. RBR Solo-T #238073		125.0 1025.0	18:04 } 20:03
745 m	Temp. Instr. RBR Solo-T #238074		140.0 1010.0	18:05 } 20:04 } Charles checked tug
755 m	Temp. Instr. RBR Solo-T #238075		150.0 1000.0	18:06 } 20:05
765 m	Temp. Instr. RBR Solo-T #238076		160.0 990.0	18:06 } 20:06
805 m	CTD Inst., w/ pres(rated 2000 m) SBE37-IMP #24286 ID 42		200.0 950.0	18:10 } 20:08

NOPP2-1 Deployed					
Hybrid Mooring (Profiler + Fixed-Depth) with 2 49-Inch Spheres and NOPP Instruments, Deployed					
By: C. Ewert		REV: M			
Source: 28-Apr-2026 11:10:41, ...NOPP/NOPP2-1/NOPP2_1_deployed/nopp2_1_deployed.cfg					
Author: 28-Apr-2026 11:10:48, cewert@PCWIN64)					
depth (incl. stretch)	component description	S/N	rope # & Length	Distance from Upper / Lower rope end	in/out of water comment

!!! Check ALL shackles for cotter pins !!!

July-7-2025

out of water
UTC time
July-28-2026

815 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T #238077 ✓		210.0 - 940.0	18:11 20:09
825 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T #238078 ✓		220.0 - 930.0	18:12 20:10
835 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T #238079 ✓		230.0 - 920.0	18:13 20:11
885 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #238080 ✓		280.0 - 870.0	18:15 20:13
895 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #207304 ✓		290.0 - 860.0	18:15 20:13
905 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #207305 ✓		300.0 - 850.0	18:16 20:14
955 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #207306 ✓		350.0 - 800.0	18:18 20:16
965 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #207307 ✓		360.0 - 790.0	18:18 20:17
975 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #207308 ✓		370.0 - 780.0	18:19 20:18
1025 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #207309 ✓		420.0 - 730.0	18:21 20:19
1035 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #207378 ✓		430.0 - 720.0	18:22 20:20
1045 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #207382 ✓		440.0 - 710.0	18:22 20:21
1205 m	CTD Inst., w/ pre-rated 2000 m)	SBE37-IMP #24271 ID 71 ✓	Stopper	600.0 550.0	18:29 20:25
1246 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #238081 ✓		640.0 - 510.0	18:31 20:28
1276 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #238082 ✓		670.0 - 480.0	18:32 20:30
1306 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #238083 ✓		700.0 - 450.0	18:33 20:31
1506 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #238084 ✓		900.0 - 250.0	18:37 20:36
1536 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #238085 ✓		930.0 - 220.0	18:38 20:38
1566 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #238086 ✓		960.0 - 190.0	18:39 20:39

Charles L. checked tag

White tag

marker

marker

marker

NOPP2-1 Deployed					
Hybrid Mooring (Profiler + Fixed-Depth) with 2 49-Inch Spheres and NOPP Instruments, Deployed					
By: C. Ewert			REV: M		
Source: 28-Apr-2026 11:10:41, ...NOPP2-1NOPP2_1_deployednop2_1_deployed.cfg					
Author: 28-Apr-2026 11:10:48, cewert@PCWIN64)					
depth (incl. stretch)	component description	S/N	rope # & Length	Distance from Upper / Lower rope end	in/out of water comment

!!! Check ALL shackles for cotter pins !!!

July-7-2025

old of water
UTC time
May-28-2026

1704 m	CTD Inst., w/ pres(rated 2000 m) SBE37-IMP	#24274 ID 74	Stopper #3 bottom PL 3/ 3/4"	1098.0 52.0	18:45	20:43
			AS 5/ 3/4" AS 5/ 2 1/2"	Insulated Termination		
1757 m	49" Float (Rated 3500 m) ADCP Instr., T-RDI 75 kHz	Apollo X7 #1374 #24608 ID 05	Stopper #4 bottom PL 3/ 3/4" #5 900m 5/16" Ins	AS 2 1/2" AS 5/ 3/4"	6.5m bypass to SW ground Standard Termination	19:07
1764 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #238087		5.0 245.0		21:04 * Come later
1794 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #238088		55.0	Picture is incorrect with S/n 238087 written	19:13 20:47
1824 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #238089		65.0 185.0	Picture is incorrect with S/n 238088 written	19:14 20:49
1955 m	CTD Inst., w/ pres(rated 3500 m) SBE37-IMP	#6363 ID 63	Stopper	196.0 54.0		19:19 21:13
1957 m	Current Meter Nortek Aquadopp	#16875 ID 06	Stopper #4 bottom PL 3/ 3/4" #5 900m 10mm Vectran Ins	198.0 52.0		19:21 21:16
2023 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #238090		14.0 886.0		19:27 21:18
2053 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #238091		44.0 856.0		19:28 21:19
2084 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #238092		74.0 826.0		19:29 21:21
2503 m	Current Meter Nortek Aquadopp	#16875 ID 06	Stopper	492.0 408.0		19:40 21:30
2505 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #238093		494.0 406.0		19:41 21:31
2915 m	8 17" Floats (8m)		#5-bottom PL 3/ 3/4" PL 3/ 3/4" #6 900m 10mm Vectran Ins	AS 3/ 5/8" AS 3/ 5/8" AS 3/ 5/8" AS 3/ 5/8"	Note: floats entangled	21:40
3193 m	Temp. Instr.	RBR Solo-T TI #238094		270.0 630.0		20:06 21:59
3194 m	CTD Inst., w/ pres(rated 7000 m) SBE37-IMP	#6355 ID 35	Stopper	271.0 629.0		20:06 21:59
3198 m	Current Meter Nortek Aquadopp	#16909 ID 08	Stopper #6 bottom	275.0 625.0		20:08 22:00

Note: line entangled

Y.2. this is also different from previous version

NOPP2-1 Deployed					
Hybrid Mooring (Profiler + Fixed-Depth) with 2 49-inch Spheres and NOPP Instruments, Deployed					
By: C. Ewert			REV: M		
Source: 28-Apr-2026 11:10:41, ...NOPPNOPP2-1NOPP2_1_deployednopp2_1_deployed.cfg					
Author: 28-Apr-2026 11:10:48, cewert@PCWIN64)					
depth (incl. stretch)	component description	S/N	rope # & Length	Distance from Upper / Lower rope end	in/out of water comment

!!! Check ALL shackles for cotter pins !!!

July-7-2025

Out of water - w/ CTD time mark - 28-2026

3829 m	8 17" Floats (8m)		PL 3/34"	AS 3/58" AS 3/58"	4x Yellow Floats	22:14
4069 m	Temp. Instr. RBR Solo-T TI #238095		10mm Vectran ins	232.0		22:26
4070 m	CTD Inst., w/ pres/rated 7000 m) SBE37-IMP #24275 ID 75		Stopper	668.0		22:26
4074 m	Current Meter Nortek Aquadopp #16359 ID 09		Stopper #7 bottom	237.0		22:27
			PL 3/34"	AS 3/58" AS 3/58"		22:40
			10mm Vectran ins	AS 3/58" AS 3/58"	Added 270m vectran	
			PL 3/34"	AS 3/58" AS 3/58"	<i>different from MOD version, I think</i>	22:45
			10mm Vectran ins	AS 3/58" AS 3/58"		
			PL 3/34"	AS 3/58" AS 3/58"		
			10mm Vectran ins	AS 3/58" AS 3/58"		
			PL 3/34"	AS 3/58" AS 3/58"		
5224 m	Temp. Instr. RBR Solo-T TI #238096		Stopper	208.0		21:32 22:49
5225 m	CTD Inst., w/ pres/rated 7000 m) SBE37-IMP #24276 ID 76		Stopper	102.0		21:34 22:49
5229 m	Current Meter Nortek Aquadopp #18506 ID 10		Stopper #11 bottom	209.0		21:36 22:51
			PL 3/34"	AS 5/34" AS 5/34"		
5329 m	8 17" Floats (8m)		PL 3/34"	AS 5/34" AS 5/34"		
5335 m	Parachute 1.00 sqm (1.13 diam)		PL 3/34"	AS 5/34"		22:56
5337 m	8 17" Floats (8m) Edgetech, 58214		PL 3/34"	AS 5/34" AS 5/34"		
	Enable: 416517		PL 3/34"	AS 5/34" AS 5/34"		
	Disable: 416534		chain 4m	AS 5/34"		
	Release: 431754		5/8" MR	AS 5/34"		
5349 m	2 Acoustic Releases Edgetech, 62320		Swivel 5/8"	AS 5/34"		22:03 22:59
	Enable: 640662		chain 0.6m	AS 5/34"		
	Disable: 640713		1/2" drop chain	AS 5/34"		
	Release: 642476		PL 3/34"	AS 5/34"		
5376 m	Anchor 2100 kg dry 1832 kg wet		chain 4m	AS 5/34"		
			5/8" MR	AS 5/34"		
			PL 3/34"	AS 5/34"		

5780 m
5789 m
5790 m

Mars + Spencer:
Release signal received 17:39:19
Released Code sent: 17:38:33
(17:42) 5412m (17:45) 5088m (18:00) 3173m
(17:56) 4623m (17:55) 3900m

Drop Time: 23:07
Drop Pos.: 49° 30.00' N, 169° 30.64' W

4.4 CPIES Recoveries

4.4.1 Recovery Notes

- No CPIES deployed at site A6.
- We were not able to recover the CPIES at A8 (SN 456; CM 264). It was sampling, but it was unresponsive to ACS commands. It's auto-release date is September 5, 2027 1200 UTC.
- Due to weather, we did not have enough time to visit site A10 (SN 448; CM 113) to recover the CPIES in 3700 m water depth, just south of the Longline Array. It's auto-release date is September 4, 2027 1200 UTC.

Inverted Echo Sounder – Model 6.1 & 6.2 Recovery

Site/Project Alutian Array/A1

IES # 445

Date: May 28, 2026 local

Year-day: _____

CM 254

<u>ACS function</u>	<u>Benthos DS-7000 & UDB9400 Command</u>
TELEM:	<u>65</u>
XPND:	<u>69</u>
BEACON:	<u>73</u>
RELEASE:	<u>61</u>
CLEAR:	<u>76</u> (valid for all IESs)

TT Measure Rate: _____ pings every _____ minutes
 Depth: 5329 meters / 94 meters/minute rise rate = 57 minutes

Transpond slant range @ release: _____ m

Release command time 9:40 pm ^{local} 9:52

Leave bottom time 9:52

Surface time 10:45 ^{expected} 10:49 → 10:48

On board time 10:57 pm

IES OFF time 11:12 pm

IES clock offset from GMT @ recovery _____ seconds (+early/- late)

Radio working? _____

Flasher working? _____

NOTES: *Had clear command underway + it was read!
 gave the ^{release} command upon approach.
 more than .5 mile away.*

time.gov IES time
 07:14:45 07:13:08

Inverted Echo Sounder - Model 6.1 & 6.2 Recovery

Site/Project Aleutians Array / A2 IES # 453
 Date: May 29, 2026
 Year-day: _____
 CM ~~453~~ 261

ACS function	Benthos DS-7000 & UDB9400 Command
TELEM:	<u>67</u>
XPND:	<u>71</u>
BEACON:	<u>75</u>
RELEASE:	<u>05</u>
CLEAR:	<u>76</u> (valid for all IESs)

TT Measure Rate: _____ pings every _____ minutes
 Depth: 5329 meters / 94 meters/minute rise rate = ~57 minutes

Transpond slant range @ release: _____ m

Release command time 12:27 am

Leave bottom time 12:40 am expected 12:42 to 12:47

Surface time 1:32 am 01:37 am - 1:33 am

On board time 1:41 am

IES OFF time 1:50 am

IES clock offset from GMT @ recovery _____ seconds (+early/- late)

Radio working? _____
 Flasher working? _____

Handwritten notes:
 $\frac{57}{1.3} = 42$
 $\frac{57}{1.3} = 42$

NOTES: *check the cm wire
 came up by the wire*

time: gov
 09:51:50

IES time
 09:49:52
~~09:51:58~~

Inverted Echo Sounder - Model 6.1 & 6.2 Recovery

Site/Project Aleutians Well Array / A3 IES # 449
 Date: May 27, 2026 local
 Year-day: _____

cm 263

<u>ACS function</u>	<u>Beathos DS-7000 & UDB9400 Command</u>
TELEM:	<u>66</u>
XPND:	<u>70</u>
BEACON:	<u>74</u>
RELEASE:	<u>01</u>
CLEAR:	<u>76</u> (valid for all IESs)

TT Measure Rate: _____ pings every _____ minutes
 Depth: 5336 meters / 94 meters/minute rise rate = 57 minutes

Transpond slant range @ release: _____ m

Release command time 4:45 PM local

Leave bottom time 5:01 PM

Surface time 5:54 expected 5:58 PM

On board time 6:03 PM local

IES OFF time 6:44 PM

IES clock offset from GMT @ recovery _____ seconds (+early/- late)

Radio working?
 Flasher working?

NOTES: Release command sent 4:45 PM ✓

402
2:45:15

105
26/05/26 02:44:10

*200m/s
 Starboard
 bow.*

Inverted Echo Sounder - Model 6.1 & 6.2 Recovery

IES # 450
 Site/Project Alentians IWR Array/A4 Date: May 27, 2026 local
 Year-day: _____
 CM 258

<u>ACS function</u>	<u>Benthos DS-7000 & UDB9400 Command</u>
TELEM:	<u>67</u>
XPND:	<u>71</u>
BEACON:	<u>75</u>
RELEASE:	<u>02</u>
CLEAR:	<u>76</u> (valid for all IESs)

TT Measure Rate: _____ pings every _____ minutes
 Depth: 5130 meters / 94 meters/minute rise rate = 54 minutes

$$\begin{array}{r} 37 \\ 15 \\ \hline 52 \end{array}$$

Transpond slant range @ release: _____ m

Release command time 7:37

Leave bottom time ? _____ should leave bottom at 7:52 or 7:57

Surface time 8:43 pm should surface at 8:46 or 8:51

On board time 9:00 pm

IES OFF time 9:24 pm

IES clock offset from GMT @ recovery _____ seconds (+early/- late)

Radio working? _____
 Flasher working? _____

NOTES: Stopped pinging midway thru the burn time
 on board AD F worked, Smoke worked but it was not pinging.

time.gps	IES time
5/28/2026	2026/5/28
05:27:00	05:26:04

Inverted Echo Sounder - Model 6.1 & 6.2 Recovery

Site/Project Aleutians Array / A5 IES # 451
 Date: started 5/27/20 local
 Year-day: _____
 cm 259

<u>ACS function</u>	<u>Benthos DS-7000 & UDB9400 Command</u>
TELEM:	<u>65</u>
XPND:	<u>69</u>
BEACON:	<u>73</u>
RELEASE:	<u>03</u>
CLEAR:	<u>76</u> (valid for all IESs)

TT Measure Rate: _____ pings every _____ minutes
 Depth: 5382 meters / 94 meters/minute rise rate = 57 minutes

Transpond slant range @ release: _____ m

Release command time 10:37 pm local

Leave bottom time 10:51 pm expect it to leave 10:52 or 10:57

Surface time 11:44 expected at 11:46 pm

On board time ~12:00 pm on board

IES OFF time 12:22 pm

IES clock offset from GMT @ recovery _____ seconds (+early/- late)

Radio working? _____

Flasher working? _____

NOTES:

time.gov IES time

08:25:30 08:24:47

37
15
10:52

10:51
57

11:00

57
9
11:46

Inverted Echo Sounder – Model 6.1 & 6.2 Recovery

IES # 454
 Site/Project Aleutians Array / A7 Date: May 28, 2026
 Year-day: _____
Cm 262

<u>ACS function</u>	<u>Benthos DS-7000 & UDB9400 Command</u>
TELEM:	<u>65</u>
XPND:	<u>69</u>
BEACON:	<u>73</u>
RELEASE:	<u>96</u>
CLEAR:	<u>76</u> (valid for all IESs)

TT Measure Rate: _____ pings every _____ minutes
 Depth: 5279 meters / 94 meters/minute rise rate = 56 minutes

Transpond slant range @ release: _____ m

Release command time 2:36 am

Leave bottom time a little before 2:50 expected 2:51 or 2:56
~~at~~ expected

Surface time _____ 3:46 or 3:43 am

On board time _____

IES OFF time 4:23 am

IES clock offset from GMT @ recovery _____ seconds (+early/- late)

Radio working? _____

Flasher working? _____

$$\begin{array}{r} 36 \\ 15 \\ \hline 51 \end{array}$$

NOTES:

time - gov IES time
 12:28:45 12:27:08

Inverted Echo Sounder - Model 6.1 & 6.2 Recovery

Site/Project Alaskan Array / A8 IES # 456
 Date: May 28, 2026 local
 Year-day: cm # 264

<u>ACS function</u>	<u>Benthos DS-7000 & UDB9400 Command</u>
TELEM:	<u>67</u>
XPND:	<u>71</u>
BEACON:	<u>75</u>
RELEASE:	<u>78</u>
CLEAR:	<u>76</u> (valid for all IESs)

TT Measure Rate: _____ pings every _____ minutes
 Depth: 5381 meters / 94 meters/minute rise rate = 57 minutes

Transpond slant range @ release: _____ m

Release command time _____

Leave bottom time _____

Surface time _____

On board time _____

IES OFF time _____

IES clock offset from GMT @ recovery _____ seconds (+early/- late)

Radio working? _____

Flasher working? _____

*7:11 PM local
Sampling
if last sample*

NOTES: *Failed recovery
 see it sampling but it is unresponsive
 to commands tried both over the side &
 through hull xbeams.*

Inverted Echo Sounder – Model 6.1 & 6.2 Recovery

Site/Project Aleutians Array / A9

IES # 457
Date: May 28, 2026
Year-day: _____
cm 265

<u>ACS function</u>	<u>Benthos DS-7000 & UDB9400 Command</u>
TELEM:	<u>65</u>
XPND:	<u>69</u>
BEACON:	<u>73</u>
RELEASE:	<u>09</u>
CLEAR:	<u>76</u> (valid for all IESs)

TT Measure Rate: _____ pings every _____ minutes
Depth: 5380 meters / 94 meters/minute rise rate = 57 minutes

Transpond slant range @ release: _____ m

Release command time 3:47 *hard to turn gain up to 9 to hear*
~~3:44 pm~~ *it during release pings*

Leave bottom time 4:00 *expected 4:02 to 4:07*

Surface time 4:53 pm *expected 4:54*

On board time 5:12 pm *on board.*

IES OFF time 5:14 pm

IES clock offset from GMT @ recovery _____ seconds (+early/- late)

Radio working? _____
Flasher working? _____

47
15
62

NOTES: *see 3:40 pm local summary. receive gain = 7*
turned it up to 9. heard it, but it is a bit sporadic

time.gov IES time
01:22:00 01:20:18

4.5 CTD Log Sheets

UTC time CTD Cast and Water Sampling Log Sheet

Ship: Sally Ride Cruise: SR2609 Operator: Yang Zhang / Charles L.
 Cast No.: 01 Water Depth: 614 Max. CTD Depth: 500m

	Start	End Downcast	End
Date	<u>2016 - May - 27</u>	<u>2016 - May - 27</u>	<u>2016 - May - 27</u>
Time	<u>20:36</u>	<u>20:49</u>	<u>21:14</u>
Latitude	<u>54° 04.63' N/S</u>	<u>54° 04.62' N/S</u>	<u>54° 04.65' N/S</u>
Longitude	<u>166° 40.10' E/W</u>	<u>166° 40.10' E/W</u>	<u>166° 40.10' E/W</u>

Preparation:

- Open bottle end caps, close spigots and air bleeds (top & bottom) < ✓
- Remove caps, tubes, syringe from sensors < ✓
- Switch on deck unit, computer, software < ✓
- Config. & data file names: SR2609.Xml/con / SR2609-CTD01.hex

Operation:

- Start data acquisition, surface values sensible? < ✓
- Bottom alarm on deck / altimeter functional? < NA >
- Pump automatically turned on? < ✓ >
- Bottom alarm at bottom / bottom echo seen by altimeter? < NA >

Water Sampling:

Rosette Bottle	CTD Data (approx.)	No Leak?	Mark cells where samples are planned. Enter sample bottle numbers during collection!			
			Press. [dbar]	Salinity		
<u>1-6</u>	<u>500</u>	<u>Leak!</u>	<u>bottle: 2, #21</u>	<u>bottle: 3, #16</u>		
<u>7-14</u>	<u>375</u>	<u>OK!</u>	<u>bottle: 7, #18</u>	<u>bottle: 8, #80</u>		
<u>15-19</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>✓</u>	<u>bottle: 15, #37</u>	<u>bottle: 18, #81</u>		
<u>20-24</u>	<u>40</u>	<u>✓</u>	<u>bottle: 21, #92</u>	<u>bottle: 23, #23</u>		

Storage:

- Release bottle water, close end caps, spigots, and air bleeds < ✓
- Rinse system, flood sensors with fresh water using syringe < ✓ >

Notes:

test
rossette bottle 1, 12, leaking

UTC time

CTD Cast and Water Sampling Log Sheet

Ship: *Sally Ride* Cruise: *SR2609* Operator: *Yang Zhang* *MOJEN SMTH*
 Cast No.: *02* Water Depth: *5301.8* Max. CTD Depth: *5285*

	Start	End Downcast	End
Date	<i>May-28-2026</i>	<i>May-28-2026</i>	<i>May-28-2026</i>
Time	<i>12:58</i>	<i>15:40</i>	<i>17:31</i>
Latitude	<i>49° 29.72' N/S</i>	<i>49° 29.72' N/S</i>	<i>49° 29.27' N/S</i>
Longitude	<i>161° 28.74' E/W</i>	<i>161° 28.75' E/W</i>	<i>161° 28.75' E/W</i>

Preparation:

- Open bottle end caps, close spigots and air bleeds (top & bottom)
- Remove caps, tubes, syringe from sensors
- Switch on deck unit, computer, software
- Config. & data file names: *SR2609.xml/com / SR2609-CTD02.hwp*

Operation:

- Start data acquisition, surface values sensible?
- Bottom alarm on deck / altimeter functional?
- Pump automatically turned on?
- Bottom alarm at bottom / bottom echo seen by altimeter?

Water Sampling:

Rosette Bottle	CTD Data (approx.)	No Leak?	Mark cells where samples are planned. Enter sample bottle numbers during collection!			
	Press. (dbar)					
✓ 3-4 ¹⁻³	5000		<i>Salinity</i>			
✓ 4-5	4500		<i>89</i>			
✓ 6-7	4000		<i>93</i>			
✓ 8-9	3500		<i>36</i>			
✓ 10-12	3000		<i>17</i>			
✓ 13-14	2500		<i>35</i>			
✓ 15-16	2000		<i>76</i>			
✓ 17-18	1550		<i>94</i>			
✓ 19-20	1050		<i>73</i>			
✓ 21-24	50		<i>85</i>			
			<i>82</i>			

Storage:

- Release bottle water, close end caps, spigots, and air bleeds
- Rinse system, flood sensors with fresh water using syringe

Notes:

*1 min soak before fire bottles.
 bottle #8 broken.*

CTD Cast and Water Sampling Log Sheet

Ship: <i>Sally Ride</i>	Cruise: <i>SR2609</i>	Operator: <i>Yang Zhang</i>
Cast No.: <i>03</i>	Water Depth: <i>4247.4 m</i>	Max. CTD Depth: <i>2000 m</i>

	Start	End Downcast	End
Date	<i>May 30 - 2016</i>	<i>May 30 - 2016</i>	<i>May 30 - 2016</i>
Time	<i>16:32</i>	<i>17:28</i>	<i>19:12</i>
Latitude	<i>53° 15' 62" N/S</i>	<i>53° 15' 62" N/S</i>	<i>53° 15' 62" N/S</i>
Longitude	<i>163° 34' 46" E/W</i>	<i>163° 34' 57" E/W</i>	<i>163° 34' 57" E/W</i>

- Preparation:
- Open bottle end caps, close spigots and air bleeds (top & bottom) <
 - Remove caps, tubes, syringe from sensors <
 - Switch on deck unit, computer, software <
 - Config. & data file names: *SR2609.xml/con / SR2609-CTD03.log* <

- Operation:
- Start data acquisition, surface values sensible? <
 - Bottom alarm on deck / altimeter functional? <
 - Pump automatically turned on? <
 - Bottom alarm at bottom / bottom echo seen by altimeter? <

Water Sampling:

Rosette Bottle	CTD Data (approx.)	No Leak?	Mark cells where samples are planned. Enter sample bottle numbers during collection!	
			Salinity X1	Salinity X2
<i>1</i> ✓ (9) 20	8	✓	<i>74</i>	<i>95</i>
✓ (3) 18	100	✓	<i>133</i>	<i>114</i>
✓ (15) 16	800	✓	<i>175</i>	<i>176</i>
✓ (3) 8	1200	✓	<i>111</i>	<i>116</i>
✓ (5) 6	2100	✓	<i>24</i>	<i>112</i>
✓ (3) 4	<i>2000</i>	✓	<i>22</i>	<i>87</i>

- Storage:
- Release bottle water, close end caps, spigots, and air bleeds <
 - Rinse system, flood sensors with fresh water using syringe <

Notes:
bottom stop. (Y.Z.)
** 2985 instead of 3000, I forgot to fire bottles.*
Salinity Sample Bottle #174 is not air tight (inner cap)

CTD Cast and Water Sampling Log Sheet

Ship: <i>Scully Ride</i>	Cruise: <i>SR2609</i>	Operator: <i>Charles Lindsey</i>
Cast No.: <i>04</i>	Water Depth: 1950m <i>4180m</i>	Max. CTD Depth: <i>1950m</i>

	Start	End Downcast	End
Date	05-24-00	05-30-26	05-30-26
Time	21:29	21:10	22:39
Latitude	<i>53° 21.63' N/S</i>	<i>53° 21.62' N/S</i>	<i>53° 21.62' N/S</i>
Longitude	<i>163° 29.23' E/W</i>	<i>163° 29.23' E/W</i>	<i>163° 29.23' E/W</i>

Preparation:

- Open bottle end caps, close spigots and air bleeds (top & bottom) < ✓ >
- Remove caps, tubes, syringe from sensors < ✓ >
- Switch on deck unit, computer, software < ✓ >
- Config. & data file names: *SR2609-CTD04.hex* | *SR2609.xmcan*

Operation:

- Start data acquisition, surface values sensible? < ✓ >
- Bottom alarm on deck / altimeter functional? < ✓ >
- Pump automatically turned on? < ✓ >
- Bottom alarm at bottom / bottom echo seen by altimeter? < NA >

Water Sampling:

Rosette Bottle	CTD Data (approx.)	No Leak?	Mark cells where samples are planned. Enter sample bottle numbers during collection!				
			Press. [dbar]	Salinity 1	Salinity 2		
<i>3-6</i>	<i>3, 9, 16</i>	<i>1950</i>		<i>110</i>	<i>119</i>		
<i>7, 8, 15, 16</i>	7, 8, 15, 16	<i>1300</i>		<i>171</i>	<i>178</i>		
<i>(17-20)</i>	17, 18, 19, 20	<i>8</i>		<i>177</i>	<i>172</i>		

Storage:

- Release bottle water, close end caps, spigots, and air bleeds < ✓ >
- Rinse system, flood sensors with fresh water using syringe < NA >

Notes:

0 → Rosette bottles for x2 Salinity Samples at same depth Y.Z.

CTD Cast and Water Sampling Log Sheet

Ship: <u>Sally Ride</u>	Cruise: <u>SR2609</u>	Operator: <u>Madison Zeena</u>
Cast No.: <u>5</u>	Water Depth: <u>4255 m</u>	Max. CTD Depth: <u>700 m</u>

	Start	End Downcast	End
Date	<u>05-30-2026</u>	<u>05-30-2026</u>	<u>05-31-2026</u>
Time	<u>23:49</u>	<u>00:06</u>	<u>01:14</u>
Latitude	<u>53° 26.69' N/S</u>	<u>53° 26.68' N/S</u>	<u>53° 26.68' N/S</u>
Longitude	<u>163° 20.41' E/W</u>	<u>163° 20.44' E/W</u>	<u>163° 20.43' E/W</u>

Preparation:

- Open bottle end caps, close spigots and air bleeds (top & bottom) < ✓ >
- Remove caps, tubes, syringe from sensors < ✓ >
- Switch on deck unit, computer, software < ✓ >
- Config. & data file names: SR2609.xml / SR2609-CTD05.hex

Operation:

- Start data acquisition, surface values sensible? < ✓ >
- Bottom alarm on deck / altimeter functional? < N/A >
- Pump automatically turned on? < ✓ >
- Bottom alarm at bottom / bottom echo seen by altimeter? < N/A >

Water Sampling:

Rosette Bottle	CTD Data (approx.)	No Leak?	Mark cells where samples are planned. Enter sample bottle numbers during collection!				
			Press. [dbar]	Salinity X1	Salinity X2		
(3,4,5)	67.8	700	✓	117	179		
(13,16,17)	18,19,20	8	✓	191	127		

Storage:

- Release bottle water, close end caps, spigots, and air bleeds < >
- Rinse system, flood sensors with fresh water using syringe < >

Notes:

○ rosette bottle for 2 salinity samples at the same depth.

4.6 Bridge's Event Log

Station Number	Date	Time	N. Latitude	W. Longitude	Remarks	Initials
Test CTD	5/25/26	12:35	54-04.630	166-40.099	CTD Deployed	KAP
		12:48	54-04.630	166-40.099	CTD at max depth	KAP
		13:16	54-04.630	166-40.099	CTD Recovered	KAP
A3	5/27/26	18:00	49-49.216	169-29.867	CPIES Recovered	SG
A4	5/27/26	21:01	49-41.645	169-47.561	CPIES Recovered	EKS
A5	5/28/26	0:02	49-29.997	169-54.595	CPIES Recovered	EKS
A7	5/28/26	4:06	49-13.969	169-29.961	CPIES Recovered	KAP
Mooring CTD	5/28/26	6:00	49-29.270	169-28.745	CTD Deployed	SG
		7:38	49-29.270	169-28.745	CTD at max depth 5296m	SG
		9:33	49-29.270	169-28.745	CTD Recovered	EKS
Mooring	5/28/26	10:28	49-30.012	169-30.039	Mooring Recovery Start	EKS
		15:00	49-31.189	169-31.490	Mooring Recovery Complete	KAP
A9	5/28/26	17:10	49-30.103	169-30.913	CPIES Recovered	SG
A8	5/28/26		No release		CPIES Not Recovered	
A1	5/28/26	22:58	49-29.914	169-04.999	CPIES Recovered	EKS
A2	5/28/26	1:39	49-41.515	169-120.070	CPIES Recovered	KAP
CTD 3000	5/30/26	8:30	53-15.676	163-39.565	CTD Deployed	EKS
		9:28	53-15.676	163-39.565	CTD at max depth 3000m	EKS
		11:15	53-15.676	163-39.565	CTD Recovered	EKS
CTD 2000	5/30/26	12:31	53-21.625	163-29.232	CTD Deployed	KAP
		13:10	53-21.625	163-29.232	CTD at max depth 1950m	KAP
		14:39	53-21.625	163-29.232	CTD Recovered	KAP
CTD 750	5/30/26	16:45	53-26.680	163-20.423	CTD Deployed	SG
		16:04	53-26.680	163-20.423	CTD at max depth 700m	SG
		17:15	53-26.680	163-20.423	CTD Recovered	EKS